

Bacteriological Profile and Antimicrobial Susceptibility Pattern in IPD Patients: A Longitudinal Study from a Tertiary Care Centre of North IndiaYadav Bhavana¹, Kaur Maninder², Kalra Neetika³^{1,2,3}Department of Microbiology, Gian Sagar Medical College and Hospital, Rajpura, Punjab, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Bacterial infections exhibit a rising trend over past years around the globe in almost every clinical setting. Bacterial infections contribute to mortality and morbidity in infected patients. Due to lack of information regarding bacterial strain responsible for infection, clinician generally tends to prescribe the patients broad spectrum antibiotics which in turn enhance the antibiotic resistance. Nowadays antibiotic resistance is a prominent concern over the globe and every effort from the health agencies has been put forward for rationale use of antibiotics.

Objective: Present study was aimed to study bacterial isolates and their antimicrobial susceptibility patterns in indoor patient department from a tertiary health care center of north India.

Methods: The various bacterial isolates isolated from different samples were collected for two years from September 2021 to September 2023 from a tertiary care centre of North India. All samples were processed in accordance with accepted laboratory practises for microbiology. The isolates were identified down to the species level and antimicrobial susceptibility tests were carried out in accordance with the Clinical Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI-2021) recommendations.

Result: Among total 2089 samples, 629 samples were positive for bacterial isolates. Among total 629 samples, 443 (70.4%) isolates were gram negative bacteria and 186 (29.6%) isolates were gram positive bacteria. Among gram negative bacteria, *Escherichia coli* was the most common bacteria identified in 273 (43.4%) samples and among gram positive bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus* was the most common bacteria identified in 133 (21.14%) samples. The Enterobacteriaceae group showed highest sensitivity against carbapenems and piperacillin-tazobactam. Highest sensitivity among all gram-positive bacteria was noted against vancomycin and linezolid. The screening of methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* with cefoxitin disc showed 52.6% (70) sensitivity.

Conclusion: The accurate determination of susceptibility patterns aids in guiding appropriate antibiotic therapy, optimizing patient outcomes, and combating the emergence of antimicrobial resistance. Continuous monitoring of resistance patterns and implementation of infection control measures are essential for effective patient management in the IPD.

Keywords: Isolates, Bacteriological profile, Antibiotic sensitivity patterns, Antibiotic resistance, Indoor patients.

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Introduction

Infections are the primary cause of mortality and morbidity globally, accounting for around 200,000 cases of fungal and bacterial infections every year with fatality rates ranging from 20 to 50% [1,2]. The most significant and prevalent types of Gram-positive bacteria include *S. aureus*, *Coagulase Negative Staphylococcus* (CoNS), *Enterococcus*, and *Streptococcus* species. Gram-negative bacteria like *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella typhi*, and *Acinetobacter* species are other significant species [3]. Identification of causative organisms and their antibiotic susceptibility is crucial for patient prognosis and effective implementation of antibiotic stewardship. Broad spectrum or

combination of antibiotics are frequently used as an empirical therapy for the patient's illness until culture and susceptibility reports are available. Broad-spectrum antibiotic usage results in antibiotic resistance, which is a major global concern [4]. The antimicrobial resistance situation in India has been exacerbated by the unrestricted sale of antibiotics. The additional elements that lead to antibiotic resistance are incorrect diagnosis, inappropriate use of antibiotics, and poor patient compliance [5]. Antibiotic-resistant bacteria are challenging to treat, have fewer treatment options, require longer hospital stays, and require larger dosages and perhaps more toxic medications. The issue is further exacerbated by the sluggish

development of new antibiotics to replace the first-line medications to which bacteria have developed resistance. Only few antimicrobials have been created and launched into clinical use in the previous 50 years. Even when a promising medication or vaccine already exists, its distribution is limited by the high production costs and the lengthy wait for regulatory clearance before use [6]. If the practitioner is well informed about the range of bacteria in various clinical specimens along with the antimicrobial susceptibility patterns common in that particular area, antibiotic therapy might be made more evidence-based. We conducted the current investigation in order to determine the most prevalent pathogens and their patterns of susceptibility in our hospital. It is possible that antibiotic susceptibility patterns in different bacteria may differ from one hospital to another and may also exhibit diversities in different geographical areas. The knowledge gained from this study will be aimed to assess the extent of antibiotics resistance among commonly isolated bacteria from routine specimens at Gian Sagar Medical College and Hospital from 2021 to 2023.

Methodology

Study design: This is a tertiary care center-based retrospective study. The bacteriological profile of samples received from In-Patient Department (IPD) in the Department of Microbiology “between” September 2021 to September 2023 were analysed in this study.

Eligibility criteria: This study included all samples having information on the patient’s demographic profile, location (ward/ICU), name of organism and antibiotic susceptibility testing. However, any isolated organism with unknown information (i.e., lack of age, gender of the patient, location, and sample type) were excluded from the study.

Sample collection and characterization: The samples received during the study period from IPD

are urine, pus, blood, endotracheal aspirate (ETA) and sputum etc. These clinical samples were gathered in accordance with the standard operating protocols and standard specimen collecting techniques. All specimens were routinely processed for aerobic cultures. The samples were inoculated on blood agar and MacConkey agar plates followed by incubation at 37°C for 18-24 hours.

When required selective media such as mannitol salt agar and xylose lysine deoxycholate agar (XLD) were used. The identification of bacterial isolates were aided with gram staining, culture characteristics, motility testing, and various biochemical tests such as coagulase test, oxidase test, triple sugar iron (TSI), indole test, urease test and citrate utilization test as described in previous studies [7]. The Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion technique was used for antimicrobial sensitivity testing in accordance with Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI - 2021) guidelines [8]. The documentation regarding patient’s age, gender and ward was retrieved from log book of Microbiology department.

Quality control (QC): The *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 and *S. aureus* ATCC 25923 were used as QC for all antimicrobial susceptibility testing and culture media.

Results

Samples from 2089 patients were screened during the study period of Sep 2021- Sep 2023, out of which 629 samples were positive for bacterial isolates. The mean age of the 629 positive patients was 47.29 ± 20.57 years with 258 (41%) males and 371 (59%) females. Among 629 positive samples, 349 (55.5%) were urine samples, 100 (15.9%) were pus samples, 82 (13.0%) were blood samples, 61 (9.7%) were respiratory samples (ETA, bronchoalveolar lavage, sputum samples etc. and 37 (5.9%) were other samples (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Distribution of clinical specimens collected from different patients.

Among total 629 samples, 443 (70.4%) samples were positive for gram negative bacteria and 186 (29.6%) samples were positive for gram positive bacteria.

Amongst isolated bacterial strains from various samples, *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli* 273, 43.4%) is the most common followed by *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*: 133, 21.1%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (*K. pneumoniae*: 56 (8.9%), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa* 42, 6.7%)

and *Acinetobacter* species in 36 (5.7%). The other less commonly isolated strains are *Coagulase-negative staphylococci* (*CoNS* 27, 4.3%), *Enterococcus* species (25, 4%), *Citrobacter* species (15, 2.4%), *Proteus* species (14, 2.2%), *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* (*S. maltophilia* 5, 0.8%), *Salmonella typhi* (2, 0.3%), *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (*St. Pneumoniae* 1, 0.2%). The distribution of isolated micro-organisms on the basis of clinical specimen is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of micro-organisms on the basis of specimens.

Name of Isolates	Urine (n=349)	Blood (n=82)	Pus (n=100)	Respiratory (n=61)	Others (n=37)	Total (n=629)
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	228 (65.3%)	11 (13.4%)	15 (15%)	12 (19.7%)	7 (18.9%)	273
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	26 (7.4%)	1 (1.2%)	7 (7%)	17 (27.9%)	5 (13.5%)	56
<i>Citrobacter</i> species	9 (2.6%)	0 (0%)	2 (2%)	2 (3.3%)	2 (5.4%)	15
<i>Acinetobacter</i> species	12 (3.4%)	4 (4.9%)	1 (1%)	18 (29.5%)	1 (2.7%)	36
<i>Proteus</i> species	3 (0.9%)	2 (2.4%)	5 (5%)	2 (3.3%)	2 (5.4%)	14
<i>Ps. aeruginosa</i>	20 (5.7%)	3 (3.7%)	8 (8%)	7 (11.5%)	4 (10.8%)	42
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	0 (0%)	2 (2.4%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2
<i>S. maltophilia</i>	0 (0%)	5 (6.1%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	5
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	33 (9.5%)	38 (46.3%)	48 (48%)	0 (0%)	14 (37.8%)	133
<i>Staphylococcus</i> species	0 (0%)	16 (19.5%)	11 (11%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	27
<i>St. pneumoniae</i>	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (1.6%)	0 (0%)	1
<i>Enterococcus</i> species	18	0 (0%)	3 (3%)	2 (3.3%)	2 (5.4%)	25

E. coli was most susceptible to meropenem (86.1%) and amikacin (86.1%) followed by piperacillin-tazobactam (82.4%), imipenem (79.5%). *E. coli* had least susceptibility to cefuroxime (27.8%) and ceftriaxone (29.7%). *Klebsiella* had shown maximum susceptibility towards carbapenems (69.6%) and least susceptibility towards cephalosporins (cefuroxime, 25.0% and ceftazidime, 30.4%).

Similar susceptibility pattern with maximum sensitivity against carbapenems was seen with *Citrobacter* species (meropenem, 93.3%), *Proteus* species (meropenem, 78.6%) and in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (76.2%). Although isolates of *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* were in lesser amount (5, 0.8%) but majority of them were sensitive to cotrimoxazole (80%) and meropenem (80%) followed by ceftazidime (60%), levofloxacin (60%) and Piperacillin-tazobactam (60%). All *S. typhi* strains (n=2) were 100% sensitive to cefixime, azithromycin,

ciprofloxacin, tetracycline, cotrimoxazole and resistant to ampicillin (50%), ceftriaxone (50%). The uro-isolates had shown maximum sensitivity for Fosfomycin followed by nitrofurantoin. Amongst Gram-positive bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *CoNS* had shown 100% sensitivity to vancomycin. The sensitivity for linezolid in *Staphylococcus aureus*, *CoNS* and *enterococcus* species is 94.7%, 96.3% and 100% respectively.

The screening of MRSA with ceftazidime showed 52.6% (70) susceptibility and 47.4% (63) resistance. *St. Pneumoniae* (n=1) was sensitive to penicillin, ceftriaxone, vancomycin, linezolid, levofloxacin and resistant to erythromycin, clindamycin and cotrimoxazole. The *enterococcus* species was sensitive to linezolid (100%), vancomycin (96%), teicoplanin (92%), nitrofurantoin (88.9%), while it was less sensitive to HLARG (68%), ampicillin (64%), erythromycin (40%) and tetracycline (40%). (Table 2 and Table 3).

Table 2: The in-vivo sensitivity profile of Gram Negative Bacteria

Antibiotics	<i>Escherichia coli</i> (n=273)	<i>Citrobacter</i> species (n=15)	<i>Klebsiella</i> species (n=56)	<i>Proteus</i> species (n=14)	<i>Acinetobacter</i> species (n=36)	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (n=42)
Cefuroxime	27.8% (76)	40.0% (6)	25.0% (14)	64.3% (9)	-	-
Cefotaxime	53.1% (145)	60% (9)	37.5% (21)	57.1% (8)	-	-
Ceftriaxone	29.7% (81)	40.0% (6)	35.7% (20)	28.6% (4)	30.6% (11)	-
Ceftazidime	44.3% (121)	53.3% (8)	30.4% (17)	28.6% (4)	30.6% (11)	64.3% (27)
Cefepime	42.5% (116)	33.3% (5)	32.1% (18)	42.9% (6)	22.2% (8)	59.5% (25)

Imipenem	79.5% (217)	86.7% (13)	69.6% (39)	64.3% (9)	55.6% (20)	64.3% (27)
Meropenem	86.1% (235)	93.3% (14)	69.6% (39)	78.6%(11)	72.2% (26)	76.2% (32)
Piperacillin-tazobactam	82.4% (225)	80.0% (12)	53.6% (30)	78.6%(11)	47.2% (17)	76.2% (32)
Gentamicin	65.2% (178)	9	60.7% (34)	57.1% (8)	-	66.7% (28)
Amikacin	86.0% (235)	66.7% (10)	66.1% (37)	35.7% (5)	47.2% (17)	59.5% (25)
Tobramycin	-	-	-	-	-	57.1% (24)
Ciprofloxacin	31.7% (92)	66.7% (10)	46.4% (26)	71.4% (10)	33.3% (12)	54.8% (23)
Levofloxacin	33.0% (90)	66.7% (10)	50.0% (28)	35.7% (5)	47.2% (17)	54.8% (23)
Cotrimoxazole	49.8% (136)	40.0% (6)	34.0% (19)	35.7% (5)	-	-
Nitrofurantoin	95.6% (/228)	100% (7/7)	65.4% (17/26)	66.7% (2/3)	91.7% (11/12)	50% (10/20)
Norfloxacin	31.6% (/228)	71.4% (5/7)	69.2% (18/26)	66.7% (2/3)	58.3% (7/12)	50% (10/20)
Fosfomycin	97.0% (221/228)	100% (7/7)	80.8% (21/26)	100% (3/3)	91.7% (11/12)	80% (16/20)

Table 3: The Sensitivity profile of Gram Positive Bacteria

Antibiotics	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (n=133)	<i>Staphylococcus species</i> (n=27)	<i>Enterococcus species</i> (n=25)
Penicillin G	30.1% (40)	55.6% (15)	-
Ampicillin	-	-	64% (16)
Cefoxitin	52.6% (70)	59.3% (16)	-
Vancomycin	100% (133)	100% (27)	96% (24)
Gentamicin	74.4% (99)	77.8% (21)	-
HLARG	-	-	68% (17)
Azithromycin	49.6% (66)	70.4% (19)	-
Erythromycin	38.3% (51)	44.4% (12)	40% (12)
Clindamycin	60.9% (81)	66.7% (18)	-
Linezolid	94.7% (126)	96.3% (26)	100% (25)
Tetracycline	57.9% (77)	66.7% (18)	40% (10)
Doxycycline	75.2% (100)	63.0% (17)	-
Teicoplanin	-	-	92% (23)
Cotrimoxazole	50.4% (67)	40.7% (11)	-
Nitrofurantoin	90.9% (30/33)	-	88.9% (16/18)
Norfloxacin	39.4% (13/33)	-	16.7% (3/18)
Ciprofloxacin	33.1% (44)	40.7% (11)	-
Levofloxacin	41.4% (55)	70.4% (19)	-

Discussion

For the effective management of cases, bacteriological profile and antibiotic susceptibility patterns are important parameters that guide the clinicians significantly. Periodic epidemiological analysis of the causative organisms and their susceptibility patterns leads to an identification of the commonly relevant pathogens in different geographical areas [9].

In our study majority of patients were females (59%) and rest of patients were males (41%). In previous studies by Rani et al. [10] and Habyarimana et al. [11], a higher proportion of males was reported which is contrary to the finding

of present study. A possible explanation for this could be due to high number of urinary tract infections samples (55.5%) in the present study which are more common in females than in males.

There is a very high variation of prevalence across the world. In present study 30.1% (629/2089) samples were true positive. Similar positivity rate was observed from a different study with positivity rate of 28% [12].

In the present study, frequency of gram-negative bacteria was higher (70.4%) compared to the gram-positive bacteria (29.6%). Similar observations were made by the Habyarimana et al. who reported high frequency of gram-negative bacteria (68.3%)

compared to gram positive bacteria (31.7%) [11]. Similar pattern have been documented in previous studies, with 51% gram negative bacteria and 45% gram positive bacteria [13]. However, other investigations have revealed that gram-positive bacteria are more common than gram negative bacteria [14]. This fluctuation may be a result of seasonal variation, regional variation or type of specimens.

In our study, *Escherichia coli* is the most common gram-negative bacteria identified in 43.4% samples whereas *S. aureus* is the most common gram-positive bacteria identified in 21.1% samples. According to Dryden, *S. aureus* is the major cause of soft tissue infections in hospitalized patients [15]. Similar observations were made by the Habyarimana et al. who reported *K. pneumoniae* (31.7%) and *S. aureus* (29.3%) as the most common bacteria among all samples [11]. Similar observations were reported by Vasudev et al [16] and Gupta et al [17] where *E. coli* was the most common organism isolated. In our study, >50% sensitivity against all bacteria was reported for imipenem, meropenem and piptaz. Similarly, Habyarimana et al. revealed that among the Gram-negative isolates, imipenem showed the highest sensitivity [11]. carbapenems were also shown by Jhahria et al. to be the most effective medication for Gram-negative bacteria [18].

In this study, among the antibiotics used for susceptibility testing for Gram positive isolates, vancomycin and linezolid showed highest activity against *S. aureus*, *CoNS*, *pneumococcus* and *enterococcus*. Similar findings were reported in the previous study by Habyarimana et al. who found that vancomycin showed highest (85.4%) activity [11]. In our study the isolated gram positive organisms were least sensitive to erythromycin. Similar findings were reported in the previous study by Rout and Rautaraya et.al. [19]. In order to be helpful for rapid patient treatment, it is crucial to regularly examine and update the epidemiology of antibiotic resistance, particularly with regard to the antibiotic susceptibility pattern of the common infections. This study is beneficial since it identifies a significant level of antibiotic resistance in the Punjab region. However, some limitations have been identified, such as the absence of correlating the antibiotic susceptibility pattern of isolated bacterial strains based on sample type.

Conclusion

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing is of utmost importance in the hospital setting. The accurate determination of susceptibility patterns aids in guiding appropriate antibiotic therapy, optimizing patient outcomes, and combating the emergence of antimicrobial resistance. The antimicrobial susceptibility testing should be part of a

comprehensive approach, which includes antimicrobial stewardship, infection control, and continuous monitoring of antibiotic resistance patterns.

Author contributions

Dr Maninder Kaur – data analysis and review, manuscript editing.

Dr Bhavana Yadav – protocol design, data collection and manuscript writing.

Dr Neetika Kalra - data collection.

Ethical clearance

We have taken ethical clearance from “Institutional Ethics Committee.”

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